

Research Paper

Method Development and its Validation for Simultaneous Estimation of Ecombination of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin as API and in Combination of Tablet Dosage Form by UV-Visible Spectrophotometry

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 27 Nov 2025

Keywords:

Metformin Hydrochloride ,
Methylcobalamin,
Simultaneous equation,
validation.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17737834

ABSTRACT

A simple, accurate, precise, rapid and economical UV-visible spectrophotometric method was developed for simultaneous estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin in a combined tablet dosage form. The estimation was carried out by simultaneous equation method for analysis of both drugs. Metformin Hydrochloride showed absorbance maxima at 232.0 nm and Methylcobalamin showed absorbance maxima at 353.0 nm using methanol as solvent. Linearity range was observed in the concentration range of 10-20 µg/ml and 1-6 µg/ml with a correlation coefficient of 0.998 and 0.999 for Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin respectively. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines. The accuracy and precision of the method was determined and validated statistically. The proposed method was successfully applied to commercial combined tablet dosage form of both drugs.

INTRODUCTION

Metformin Hydrochloride[MET] is chemically N,N-Dimethylimidodicarbonimidic diamide [Figure 1]. It is hypoglycemic agent. It is used in the treatment of type 2 diabetes[1],[2],[3],[4] and is official in Indian Pharmacopoeia 2010.

Figure1. Metformin Hydrochloride

Methylcobalamin[MEC] is chemically carbanide;cobalt(3+);[(2~{R},3~{S},4~{R},5~{S

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

)5(5,6dimethylbenzimidazolyl)4hydroxy2(hydroxymethyl)oxolan3yl]1[3[(1~{R},2~{R},3~{R},5~{Z},7~{S},10~{Z},12~{S},13~{S},15~{Z},17~{S},18~{S},19~{R})-2,13,18-tris(2-amino-2-oxoethyl)-7,12,17-tris(3-amino-3-oxopropyl)3,5,8,8,13,15,18,19octamethyl2,7,12,17tetrahydro1~{H}corrin24id3yl]propanoylamino]propan-2-yl phosphate [Figure 2]. It is used in the treatment of peripheral neuropathy, megaloblastic anemia [6],[7] and is official in British Pharmacopoeia 2012, United States Pharmacopoeia 2011 and Indian Pharmacopoeia 2010.

Figure 2. Methylcobalamin

Literature survey reveals spectrophotometric [10],[11],[12],[13], HPLC, HPTLC and other methods for the estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin individually and in combination with other drugs. However, no method has been reported so far in any literature for the simultaneous estimation of these two drugs in combined dosage form. Therefore aim of the research was to develop and validate simple, accurate, precise and specific UV spectrophotometric method for simultaneous estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin in pharmaceutical tablet dosage form.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Apparatus:

A double beam UV-VIS Spectrophotometer (UV 1800, Shimadzu, Japan) Spectral bandwidth of 1 nm and wavelength accuracy of ± 0.5 nm with a pair of 1 cm matched quartz cells was used to measure the absorbance of all the solutions. Spectra were automatically obtained by UV- Probe system software (UV Probe version 2.31). All weights were taken on Digital electronic balance Sartorius, CP225D.

Reagents and chemicals:

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Methanol A.R. grade was procured from Loba Chem. Ltd., Mumbai. Metformin Hydrochloride was kindly supplied by Cadila Healthcare Ltd., Ahmedabad and Methylcobalamin was kindly supplied by Torrent Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Mehsana (Gujarat) as a gift sample.

Marketed formulation:

The commercial fixed dose combination tablet Sugament MC (Metformin Hydrochloride 250 mg and Methylcobalamin 750 mcg) was procured from local market.

Preparation of standard stock solutions:

An accurately weighed quantity of Metformin Hydrochloride (10 mg) and Methylcobalamin (10 mg) were transferred to a separate 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved and sonicated in methanol and final volume was adjusted to the mark with methanol to get a standard solution containing 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of each drug.

Determination of wavelength of maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) for Metformin Hydrochloride:

Standard solution of Metformin Hydrochloride (1ml) was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask. The volume was adjusted to 10 ml with methanol as solvent. The absorbance of the final solution (10

$\mu\text{g/ml}$) was scanned in the range 800-200 nm against methanol as blank and λ_{max} was found to be 232.0 nm.

Figure 3: UV scan for determination of λ_{max} of Metformin Hydrochloride

Determination of wavelength of maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) for Methylcobalamin:

Standard solution of Methylcobalamin (1 ml) was transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask. The volume

was adjusted to 10 ml with methanol as solvent. The absorbance of the final solution (5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was scanned in the range 800 to 200 nm against methanol as blank and λ_{max} was found to be 353.0 nm. [Figure 4].

Figure 4 : UV scan for determination of λ_{max} of Methylcobalamin

Preparation of calibration curve of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin:

Standard solutions of Nebivolol Hydrochloride in the concentration range of 6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ to 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

were prepared by transferring 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8 and 2.0 ml of Metformin Hydrochloride stock solution (100 ppm) to a series of eight volumetric flasks of 10 ml and standard solutions of Methylcobalamin in the concentration

range of 2 µg/ml to 7 µg/ml were prepared by transferring 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6 and 0.7 ml of Methylcobalamin stock solution (100 ppm) to a series of six volumetric flasks of 10 ml. The volume in each volumetric flask was made up with

methanol as solvent. The absorbance of the solutions were measured at both the wavelength 281.5 nm and 240.0 nm against the methanol as blank and calibration curves were plotted [Figure 5] [Figure 6]

Figure 5 : Calibration curve for Metformin HCl at 232.0 nm

Figure 6 : Calibration curve for Metformin HCl at 353.0 nm

Figure 7 : Calibration curve for Methylcobalamin at 232.0 nm

Figure 8 : Calibration curve for Methylcobalamin at 353.0 nm

Preparation of synthetic API mixture of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin:

The synthetic API mixture of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin was prepared in ratio of 10:1. Accurately weighed 100 mg of Metformin Hydrochloride and 30 mg of Methylcobalamin were transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, 100 ml of methanol as solvent was added to it upto quantity sufficient. Further 10 ml of prepared solution (1000 μ g per ml) was transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. The volume was adjusted to 100 ml with methanol as solvent. The final standard stock solution contain 100 μ g per ml of Metformin Hydrochloride and 30 μ g per ml of Methylcobalamin.

Estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin in synthetic mixture:

The API synthetic mixture (0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8 and 2.0 ml) was transferred to a series of seven volumetric flask of 10 ml and volume was made up to mark using methanol as solvent. The absorbances of these solutions were measured at 232.0 nm and 353.0 nm wavelength.

Amount of each drug was determined by using simultaneous equation as following formula^{[21],[22]}:

$$C_{MET} = \frac{(A_2 a_{y1} - A_1 a_{y2})}{(a_{x2} a_{y1} - a_{x1} a_{y2})} \text{-----(1)}$$

and

$$C_{MEC} = \frac{(A_1 a_{x2} - A_2 a_{x1})}{(a_{x2} a_{y1} - a_{x1} a_{y2})} \text{-----(2)}$$

where,

- C_{MET} = Concentration of Metformin Hydrochloride in g/L
- C_{MEC} = Concentration of Methylcobalamin in g/L
- A_1 = Absorbance of mixture at 232.0 nm
- A_2 = Absorbance of mixture at 353.0 nm
- a_{x1} = Absorptivity of Metformin Hydrochloride at 232.0 nm
- a_{x2} = Absorptivity of Metformin Hydrochloride at 353.0 nm
- a_{y1} = Absorptivity of Methylcobalamin at 232.0 nm
- a_{y2} = Absorptivity of Methylcobalamin at 353.0 nm

Validation of proposed method:

The proposed method was validated according to International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines:

Specificity:

The synthetic mixture of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin was prepared in ratio of 10:1. Common excipients used in the tablet formulation were added into this mixture. The absorbance was measured before addition of excipients and after addition of excipients at 232.0 nm and 353.0 nm.

Linearity and Range:

Aliquots of standard stock solutions of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin were taken in 10 ml volumetric flasks and diluted with methanol to get final concentration in the range of 10-60 µg/ml for Metformin Hydrochloride and 1-6 µg/ml for Methylcobalamin. This calibration range was prepared six times and absorbances were measured at 232.0 nm and 353.0 nm for each drug separately.

Accuracy:

The accuracy of the method was determined by carrying out recovery studies using standard addition method. Known amounts of standard solutions of MET and MEC were added to prequantified sample solutions of MET and MEC (5 µg/ml MET and 15 µg/ml MEC). The amounts of MET and MEC were estimated by applying obtained values to the respective regression line equations. The experiment was repeated for three times.

Method Precision (Repeatability):

The precision of the method was checked by repeated scanning and measurement of absorbance of solutions ($n = 6$) for MET (5 µg/ml) and MEC (15 µg/ml) without changing the parameter of the proposed spectrophotometry method.

Intermediate Precision (Reproducibility):

The intraday and interday precision of the proposed method was determined by analyzing the corresponding responses 3 times on the same day at 2 hours interval and on 3 different days over a period of 1 week for 3 different concentrations of standard solutions of MET and MEC (4,5,6 µg/ml for MET and 12,15,18 µg/ml for MEC). The result was reported in terms of relative standard deviation (% RSD).

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification:

The limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantification (LOQ) of the drug were calculated using the following equations designated by International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \text{SD}/S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \text{SD}/S$$

Where,

- SD = the standard deviation of the response
- and S = slope of the calibration curve

LOD and LOQ were determined from the standard deviations of the responses for six replicate determinations.

Robustness:

Solution containing mixture of 5 µg/ml MET and 15 µg/ml MEC was prepared from the standard stock solution (100 µg/ml of MET and 30 µg/ml of MEC) through dilution. Prepared solution was analyzed as per proposed method with small but deliberate change in λ_{max} . ($\lambda_{\text{max}} \pm 1 \text{ nm}$) and scanning speed (slow, medium and fast).

Estimation of Nebivolol Hydrochloride and Indapamide in combined tablet dosage form:

Twenty tablets were weighed and average weight was calculated and finally powdered. An accurately weighed quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg of MET and 3 mg of MEC was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask and mixed with 70 ml of methanol as a solvent and solution was sonicated for 20 minutes. There after volume was made up to 100 ml with the same solvent to produce the resultant solution of 100 µg/ml and 30 µg/ml of MET and MEC respectively. The solution was filtered through Whatmann filter paper 42. From the filtrate, 1.3 ml was transferred to five different 10 ml volumetric flasks and volume in each was made up to 10 ml with methanol as a solvent. Absorbances of these solutions i.e. A1 and A2 were measured at 232.0 nm and 353.0 nm using methanol as blank. Values of the A1 and A2 were substituted in Eqn. 1 and 2 to obtain the concentration of MET and MEC respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validation:

Specificity:

The developed method was found to be specific as percent interference obtained was 0.461% and 0.369% for MET and MEC respectively, which were less than prescribed limit (0.5%) as per ICH guidelines. Thus it was concluded that the addition of excipients had a very negligible change in the concentration of MET and MEC.

Linearity and Range:

Linearity range was found to be 10.0 - 60.0 µg/ml for MET at 232.0 nm and 353.0 nm. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.999 & 0.998 which showed good linearity between ranges. The slope was found to be 0.049 & 0.005 and intercept was found to be 0.022 and -0.002.

For MEC at 232.0 nm and 353.0 nm, linearity range was found to be 1.0 – 6.0 µg/ml. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.997 & 0.999 which showed good linearity between ranges. The slope was found to be 0.022 and 0.091 and intercept was found to be 0.003 and -0.006 [Table 1].

Accuracy

The results obtained for the accuracy study (recovery method) from three sample studies (n = 3) for each level indicated that the mean of the % recovery was 99.637% and 99.484% and % RSD was 0.828 % and 0.833 % for MET and MEC respectively in synthetic mixture. The method was found to be accurate [Table 2].

Method Precision (Repeatability)

Repeatability study showed a RSD of 0.597 % for MET and 0.529 % for MEC, which was less than 2%.

Intermediate Precision (Reproducibility)

The method was found to be precise as intra-day precision study showed a RSD of 0.08% for MET and a RSD of 0.60% for MEC and inter-day precision study showed a RSD of 0.33% for MET and a RSD of 0.74 % for MEC. The % RSD values were less than 2% [Table 3].

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification

The LOD was found to be 0.259µg/ml and 0.194 µg/ml and LOQ was found to be 0.786 µg/ml and 0.589 µg/ml for MET and MEC respectively which represents that sensitivity of the method was high.

Robustness

The robustness study for change in scanning speed showed a RSD of 0.195% and 0.825% for MET and MEC respectively. The robustness study for change in λ_{\max} showed a RSD of 0.472% and 0.194% for MET and MEC respectively. The

method was found to be robust at small variations in scanning speed and λ_{\max} [Table 3].

Summary of all validation parameters is shown in [Table 3].

Table 1: Data showing recovery study

Sr. No	WL. (nm)	Conc. of tablet sol ⁿ (ppm)	Std. Added (ppm)	Amt. Found (mg)	Mean Recovery \pm SD	% RSD
1.	232	5	4.00	17.066	MET	MET
	353	15	1.20	5.113	99.637 \pm 0.825	0.828
2.	232	5	5.00	18.013	MEC	MEC
	353	15	1.50	5.430		
3.	232	5	6.00	18.956	99.484 \pm 0.829	0.833
	353	15	1.80	5.643		

Table 2: Data showing Intra and inter day precision analysis

Method	MET		MEC	
	Mean* \pm SD	% RSD	Mean* \pm SD	% RSD
Simultaneous equation method	3.833 \pm 0.0418	1.117	14.702 \pm 0.0308	0.204

Table 3 : Summary of validation parameters by UV-Visible spectrophotometry method

Validation parameters		Simultaneous Equation	
		MET	MEC
Specificity (% interference)		0.083	0.126
Range (μg/ml)	Linear range	10-60	1-6
	Working range	08- 60	0.8-6
	Target conc.	35	3.5
	Target range	28,35 & 42	2.8, 3.5 & 4.2
Accuracy (% recovery)		99.46 %	99.96 %
Precision (% RSD)	Repeatability	0.597	0.529
	Intra day	0.101	0.648
	Inter day	0.602	0.451
LOD (μg/ml)		0.259	0.194
LOQ (μg/ml)		0.786	0.589
Robustness (% RSD)	Change in scanning speed	0.457	0.624
	Change in WL	0.472	0.194

CONCLUSION

The results of the analysis of pharmaceutical tablet formulation by the proposed U.V. spectrophotometric method were highly reproducible and reliable and were in good agreement with the label claim of the drug. The additives usually present in the pharmaceutical formulations of the assayed samples did not interfere with determination of MET and MEC.

The observations and results obtained from this study including linearity, accuracy and precision (method precision as repeatability and intermediate precision as intra and inter day precision) were lie well within acceptable limits. From the experimental studies it was concluded that proposed method was simple, sensitive, economic, precise, accurate and specific and can be adopted for the routine quality control analysis

of both drugs in combined tablet formulation without interference of excipients.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to Cadila Healthcare Ltd., Ahmedabad and Torrent Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Mehsana (Gujarat) for providing gift sample of MET and MEC, respectively to carry out the research work. The authors are highly thankful to Lachoo Memorial College of Science and Technology (Autonomous), Jodhpur, Pharmacy Wing for providing all the facilities to carry out the research work.

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HOW TO CITE: Shrey Parmar, Ajay Gaur, B. P. Nagori, Priya Kumawat, Method Development and its Validation for Simultaneous Estimation of Ecombination of Metformin Hydrochloride and Methylcobalamin as API and in Combination of Tablet Dosage Form by UV-Visible Spectrophotometry, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 11, 4482-4491. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737834>

